

THE FRACTURE OF FIBER-REINFORCED METAL MATRIX

COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Abstract

The strength of metal matrix materials reinforced with unidirectional brittle fibers is shown to be best described in terms of upper and lower bounds. Composites with strengths near the expected lower bound behave as a bundle in which the matrix carries relatively little load and transfers no stress by shear. Conversely, increased stress transfer takes place in the matrix of those materials with strengths that approach the upper bound. Tensile strength and fracture toughness values were obtained from 6061 aluminum reinforced with boron or silicon carbide fibers. The as-received, heat treated and thermally fatigued conditions were investigated and similar tests were carried out on cross-plyed, 0/90°, boron reinforced material. The results obtained from all specimens indicated that the presence of a very small crack produced a disproportionately large decrease in the strength of the material. Thereafter, an increase in the slot length resulted in a smaller degradation of the load bearing ability. The failure of the slotted specimens is discussed in terms of strength bounds similar in concept to those proposed to describe the tensile strength results as discussed above.

Introduction

The failure of composite materials comprised of a matrix reinforced with strong, stiff fibers has been the subject of many individual papers and review articles. The mechanism of failure depends sensitively on the type of fiber used as the reinforcement. For example, metallic fibers fail at a unique stress level; thus, failure of one fiber and failure of a matrix reinforced with them will occur simultaneously if the failure strain of the fibers is less than the matrix and if the volume fraction of reinforcement is above a critical amount. Conversely, brittle fibers fail over a range of stresses. If a simple bundle of these type of fibers is loaded, some of them will break at a low stress and will not thereafter contribute to the load bearing capability of the bundle. On further loading an increasing number of fibers will become broken until those remaining can no longer support the applied stress and the bundle will fail. This "bundle" failure of brittle fibers has been adequately described by Daniels [1] and Coleman [2].

It has been demonstrated repeatedly that surrounding a bundle of brittle fibers with a matrix will produce a composite whose strength is far greater than can be accounted for by simply adding together the load carrying capability of the matrix and the bundle. A model which describes this synergistic strengthening effect has been discussed in a series of papers that have been published and recently reviewed by Rosen [3]. Rosen argued that a single break in a fiber would not remove the load bearing capability of that fiber from the total bundle, for stress transfer would take place through the matrix. This local shear process would transfer load around the break and to adjacent fibers. In effect, the load would rapidly build up in the broken fiber from a value of zero at the point of separation to a value equal to that carried by the rest of the fibers in the cross-section. This shear lag mechanism of stress transfer had been discussed earlier by Cox [4] and others [5,6]. The length of fiber that is subjected to the increasing stress is termed "ineffective". Obviously, further breaks in the fiber are not expected in this length; however, breakage of adjacent fibers might be expected for they are all considered to be overloaded locally. A composite is considered to be made up of many of these small bundles, or links, connected in series. Failure of the total composite is considered to occur when one of the bundles fails. Notwithstanding, failure of each individual bundle, or link, is considered to take place by a bundle mechanism.

Zweiben and Rosen [7] and Zweiben [8] pointed out that a break in an individual fiber could simply overload only those fibers immediately adjacent to the broken one. If these fibers break, failure of the total composite would then occur by a process similar to crack propagation. The above authors used the stress concentration factors computed by Hedgepeth [9] and Hedgepeth and

Van Dyke [10] to calculate the probable numbers of multiple fiber breaks that could be present immediately prior to failure of a glass-fiber reinforced epoxy tensile test specimen. Inherent in these calculations are the two important assumptions that the matrix or matrix-fiber bond strength will be sufficient to inhibit splitting parallel to the fibers and the matrix will not deform plastically. Matrix plasticity is particularly important when metal matrix composites are considered, for a large plastic zone would be expected to distribute the excess load associated with a broken fiber over an area that would include many continuous fibers. Thus, the magnitude of the stress in the fibers immediately adjacent to the broken one would be reduced to a value appreciably less than that given by the Hedgepeth analysis.

Wright and Wills [11] discussed the strengths of as-received and thermally fatigued aluminum-boron composites in terms of both the cumulative damage and the crack propagation theories of failure noted above. They noted that the cumulative theories appeared to describe the room temperature mechanical property values they obtained from thermally fatigued specimens. However, it was difficult to determine the probable fracture mode of the as-received material. This problem centered on the results of a calculation using Hedgepeth's stress concentration factors which indicated that the stress in the fibers adjacent to small multiple groups of fiber breaks could be similar in magnitude to that at the tip of a macroscopic crack. As pointed out by the authors, local plasticity would undoubtedly change the magnitude of the local stresses. However, failure by crack propagation in both notched and unnotched specimens could not be entirely disregarded. Wright and Iannuzzi [12] effectively continued the investigation by testing centre slotted specimens of unidirectionally reinforced boron fiber-6061 aluminum alloy. They found that the failure stress of the slotted specimens could be arranged to follow a square root of crack length dependence if the appropriate extent of stable crack growth were added to the initial crack length. It therefore appeared that the concepts of linear elastic fracture mechanics could be applied to a metal matrix material reinforced with a strong stiff fiber of the boron type.

In this paper is presented the results of further work carried out on centre slotted specimens of 6061-aluminum reinforced with various fiber materials. The results are initially discussed in terms of upper and lower strength bounds that assume totally plastic or totally elastic response of the material respectively. It is finally concluded that a plastic zone exists at the crack tip that can be modeled to predict the upper bound failure stress of any of the metal matrix composites investigated. A lower strength bound equal to the strength of a bundle is obtained by assuming that tensile or shear stresses are not carried by the matrix.

Experimental Techniques

Test Specimens

The test material was fabricated by the Amercom Corporation using a proprietary diffusion bonding technique. In general, the process consisted of applying a pressure of several thousand pounds per square inch to foil-filament arrays at a temperature of about 500° C. The organic binder which was used to maintain the integrity of the original material was burnt off during the diffusion bonding operation. After fabrication the material was cooled in air by placing the composite panel on a large aluminum heat sink.

The specimens were cut from each master panel using the Electric Discharge Machining (EDM) process. All specimens were either 6 or 12 inches long, and the thickness varied between 0.040 and 0.086 inches.

The width of the tensile or fracture specimens was 0.5 or 1.0 inches respectively. The notch width of the fracture specimen was kept constant, equal to 0.02 inches, and the root radius was maintained at 0.0015 inches.

Specimens were tested with the matrix material in the as-received, solution treated or fully hard (T6) condition. The solution treatment consisted of quenching the individual cut and notched specimens in water after being held at a temperature of 527° C for 35 minutes. The T6 condition was achieved by maintaining the solution treated specimens at 177° C for 8 hours followed by cooling in air.

Aluminum tabs 0.5 or 1 inch wide, 1.5 inches long and 0.04 inches thick were bonded to the ends of each specimen using Eccobond adhesive. For the fracture specimens small gauge blocks 0.25 inches long, 0.15 inches wide, were bonded 0.2 inches apart across the centre slot and the separation of these blocks during loading was monitored using a clip gauge. This technique enabled the determination of the stress at which initial crack extension took place.

Individual fibers were extracted from selected specimens by dissolving the matrix in a caustic soda solution. The mean strengths of the various fiber lengths were then determined by loading individual fibers in an Instron tensile test machine using pneumatic grips operating at about 70 psig. The fibers were handled at the ends to avoid damaging the gauge length and the grips of the tensile test machine were protected with aluminum to distribute the load evenly and to avoid crushing the fibers. The fiber gauge length was set using the dials present on the machine.

Results

i. Verification of Reinforcement Content.

6061 Aluminum matrix specimens reinforced with unidirectional boron or silicon carbide fibers were tested. Additional tests were carried out on the same matrix material reinforced with boron fibers arranged in 0/90 ° orientation. The volume fraction of reinforcement present in each panel was computed by counting the numbers of fibers that were present in a given specimen cross-section. The total number of fibers was then multiplied by the mean area of one fiber and the resulting area of reinforcement was then divided into that of the total specimen in order to calculate the respective volume fraction. The results indicated that the boron materials contained either 47 v/o, 27 v/o or 40 v/o (0/90) reinforcement. The remaining material investigated contained 34 v/o SiC.

ii. Individual Fiber Tests.

Fibers were extracted from numerous selected specimens and the mean strengths and standard deviations were computed for 0.5, 1 and 2 inch gauge length specimens. Cumulative distribution functions were calculated from the respective strength values using 20 ksi stress intervals and the data was arranged so that the results could be used to compute the appropriate materials parameters necessary for inclusion in the Weibull expression [13],

$$G(\sigma) = 1 - \exp \left[-L/D(\sigma - \sigma^*) / \sigma_0 \right] \quad -1$$

where

- $G(\sigma)$ = cumulative frequency
- σ_0 = distribution scale factor
- ω = distribution shape factor (describes scatter of data)
- σ^* = lower limiting strength (assumed equal to 0 psi)
- L/D = fiber length to diameter ratio

For this work the Weibull parameters σ_0 and ω were obtained graphically using the procedures noted in [11]. The mean strength and the strength of a bundle of fibers of length L was then calculated using the respective expressions:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \sigma_0 (L/D)^{-1/\omega} \Gamma(1 + 1/\omega) \quad -2$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ is the mean fiber strength and Γ is the gamma function

also:
$$\sigma_B = \sigma_0 \left[L/D \omega e \right]^{-1/\omega} \quad -3$$

where σ_B is the bundle strength

A summary of the data is shown in table I. All the data appears to substantiate the currently accepted theories of brittle fracture for the mean strength of the shorter fibers is the greater, and the bundle strength is always less than the corresponding mean strength.

Table I

Type	Statistical Strength Data of Fiber Reinforcements					
	Diameter (ins)	ω	σ_o (ksi)	$\bar{\sigma}$ (ksi) 1"	σ_B (ksi) 1"	3"
SiC	0.0040	8.663	707.40	382	253	229
B	0.0056	6.71	1044.15	452	315	267

iii. Fracture Characteristics of Slotted Specimens.

a. As-received

The fracture stresses of notched specimens of 6061 aluminum reinforced with 34 v/o SiC, 47 and 27 v/o boron arranged unidirectionally and similar specimens reinforced with 40 v/o cross-pliied 0/90° boron fibers are shown in tables II and III. It can be noted that the presence of a slot in all of these materials reduced the strength. The percentage degradation was largest for the smaller crack lengths and decreased as the crack length increased. This effect had been reported by others [14,15] who further noted that the net stress at failure appeared to be constant for the larger crack lengths.

b. Heat Treated Matrix Materials

The fracture of specimens that were tested with the matrix in the solution treated and the fully hardened T-6 condition are also shown in the tables. In contrast to the results usually obtained from very strong materials, the strength values obtained from these unslotted or slotted specimens were in general, greater than those exhibited by the as-received or solution treated specimens.

c. Extended Length Specimens

Specimens 12 inches long were tested with the matrix in the as-received condition and these results are also included in the tables. There appears to be no significant difference between these values and those obtained from the shorter specimens.

Table II

Fracture Stress of Notched Specimens of 6061 Aluminum Reinforced
with 47 v/o Boron Fibers

Speciman	t (in)	l (in)	2a (in)	Fracture Stress (ksi)		
				A	B	C
W 1	0.040	6	0	200		
2			0.20	116		
3			0.25	98		
4			0.37	94		
5			0.50	71		
6			0.65	52		
7	0.060	6	0	197		
8			0.20	101		
9			0.25	100		
10			0.37	79		
11			0.50	67		
12			0.65	45		
13	0.086	6	0			
14			0.20	98		
15			0.25	93		
16			0.37	79		
17			0.50	60		
18			0.65	42		
19	0.082	6	0		226	232
20			0.11			
21			0.21		107	109
22			0.31		85	90
23			0.41		77	81
24			0.51		67	64
25	0.050	12	0	216		
26			0.11	137		
27			0.21	112		
28			0.31	100		
29			0.41	82		
30			0.51	71		

X= 27 v/o Boron; Y = 34 v/o SiC fibers; Z = 40 v/o 0/90°
cross-plyed; A= as received; B= Quenched; C= Quenched and
Aged.

t= thickness; l = length; 2a = crack length.

Table III

Fracture Stress of Notched Specimens of 6061 Aluminum Reinforced with Various Fiber Reinforcements.

Specimen	t (in)	l (in)	2a (in)	Fracture Stress (ksi)		
				A	B	C
X 1	0.065	6	0	105		
2			0.11	81.		
3			0.25	57.		
4			0.35	53.		
5			0.50	38.		
6			0.041	6	0	
7	0.11				51	70
8	0.21				44	48
9	0.31				43	45
10	0.41				33	35
11	0.51				24	31
Y 1	0.030	6	0	72		
2			0.10	61		
3			0.25	57		
4			0.35	47		
5			0.50	41		
Z 1	0.065	6	0	104		
2			0.1	49		
3			0.25	40		
4			0.35	33		
5			0.50	28		

X = 27 v/o Boron; Y= 34 v/o SiC fibers; Z= 40 v/o 0/90° cross-plyed; A= as received; B= Quenched; C= Quenched and Aged.
t = thickness; l = length; 2a = crack length.

Discussion

The prediction of the strength of a composite material from a knowledge of the strengths of the individual components is a desirable goal, for then routine component or materials testing could be eliminated. In addition, expressing the strength of slotted specimens as a single valued function containing both stress and crack length is advantageous from engineering design considerations. The search for such a materials parameter has created increasing interest in the field of fracture mechanics. Here the strength of slotted specimens is expressed in terms of a critical stress intensity factor, k_c , where, for an infinitely wide elastic specimen containing a through crack of length $2c$:

$$k_c = \sigma_c (\pi c)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{--4}$$

σ_c is the failure stress of the specimen.

Rearranging (4) we obtain

$$\sigma_c = k_c (\pi c)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{--5}$$

For most metallic materials, the values of k_c that are obtained from experiments are dependent on the relative size of the plastic zone that exists at the crack tip. Effectively, the values of k_c increase as the plastic zone size increases. When the plastic zone is relatively large, then the stress concentration effect of the notch is removed, equations (4) and (5) do not apply and then, the failure stress of the notched specimen is given by:

$$\sigma = \sigma_u (w - 2c)/w \quad \text{--6}$$

σ_u is the ultimate tensile strength of the material. It is to be noted that the strength of any material should fall between a lower bound of strength, such as given by (5), and an upper bound such as given by (6).

In practice, these bounds are widely separated and cannot be used effectively in engineering design. However, in the following, the principles are applied to fiber reinforced composite materials for it is to be noted that the bounds are closer together.

i. Elastic Case. (Lower Bound)

If the matrix and fiber behave in an elastic manner then the stress in the first fiber adjacent to a notch can be calculated using the expressions generated by McClintock [16] as referenced by Argon [17]. For this work however, the maximum stress in this first fiber was calculated using the elastic stress concentration factors, K_n , resulting from the shear lag analysis of Hedgepeth, et al. Forⁿ the two dimensional case:

$$K_n = 4.6.8 \dots (2n + 2) / 3.5.7 \dots (2n + 1) \quad \text{--7}$$

where n is the number of cut fibers. The stress concentration factors calculated using (7) are shown in Table IV. It was reasoned that the two dimensional results were more appropriate to the longer crack lengths. However, the stress concentration factors associated with a square three dimensional network are also shown and these were used for calculations where n was very small.

Table IV

Elastic Stress Concentration Factors Associated with Multiple Broken Fibers.

Number of Cut Fibers	Elastic Stress Concentration Factor	Equivalent Crack Length			
		W	X	Y	Z
1	1.14 (3D)	.0125	0.022	.0123	.0146
2	1.18 (3D)	.025	0.044	.0246	.0292
3	1.46 (3D)	.037	.066	.0369	.0440
10	2.97 (2D)	.125	0.22	.123	.146
20	4.09 (2D)	.25	.44	.246	.292
24	4.45 (2D)	.30	.53	.296	.352
48	6.22 (2D)	.60	1.05	.591	.704

W= 47 v/o Boron; X = 27 v/o Boron; Y = 34 v/o SiC; Z= 40 v/o 0/90° Boron; 3D = three dimensional square array [10]

If one effectively ignores the effect of variations in the strength of individual brittle fibers one can postulate that a given crack in a composite material will begin to propagate when the product of the applied stress and the stress concentration factor associated with that crack becomes identical to the fracture stress of the first fiber immediately adjacent to the slot. By the same reasoning, once this first fiber fails, all of the adjacent fibers will fail, for the stress concentration factor increases as the slot length increases. Effectively, the crack front will accelerate across the specimen. Using this reasoning, the fracture strength of a slotted specimen will be identical to the tensile strength of a parallel sided specimen divided by the stress concentration factor associated with the notch. Before computing the failure stress of notched composites however, it is necessary to determine the length of the crack that produces failure of a parallel sided test piece. Wright and Wills have indicated that immediately prior to failure, it would be possible for three fiber breaks to exist side by side in a specimen containing 47 v/o fibers similar to the type used here. The failure stress of specimens containing larger cracks can then be computed. Two adjacent fiber breaks are more likely in the specimens containing the smaller volume fractions of reinforcement. The calculated strengths are designated 'Hedgepeth' curves and are compared to the experimental strength values in figs. 1-3. It is to be noted that the strengths exhibited by the metal matrix materials used in this work are, for the most part, greater than those predicted. Therefore, the strengths calculated by assuming a totally elastic response from the specimen represent the lowest strengths possible.

ii. Plastic Case (Upper Bound)

It must be emphasized that it was assumed in the calculation just discussed that the matrix and the fibers behaved elastically as they were stressed to fracture. Also, the matrix-fiber bond strength was assumed to be effectively infinite. In a real metal-matrix composite of the type investigated here, these assumptions of high bond strength and no plasticity in the matrix would appear to be questionable.

Various investigators have indicated that matrix plasticity would lower the stress concentration values [10][18], and Olster and Jones [19] have discussed the bulbous geometry of the plastic zone in these boron fiber reinforced aluminum materials. Thus, the appropriate stress concentration values are probably less than those presented in table IV. A quantitative calculation of the actual reduction in the local stress concentration factor caused by plasticity effects and/or variable bond strengths is quite complex; however, in the limit, with unrestrained plastic flow in the matrix and no work hardening, or complete debonding at all of the matrix-fiber interfaces, the strength values will become identical to the strength of a simple bundle with a length equal to the length of the specimen. This strength, when multiplied by the fiber volume fraction and the ligament length: width ratio would be an upper strength bound for a slotted specimen.

The variation in the upper strength bounds resulting from the presence of cracks of different sizes is included in figs. 1-3. Inspection of the data plotted at zero crack length indicates that the strength of a bundle of fibers is appreciably less than the strength of a parallel sized test specimen as discussed previously [11][20]. The strength of a bundle decreases linearly as the crack length increases. This contrasts the very large initial strength degradation to be expected from the presence of small cracks if the specimen is considered to behave in a totally elastic manner to failure. Inspection of the experimental strength values indicate that most of them fall on or near the upper strength bound. Thus, failure by a bundle mechanism is strongly suggested. An increasing deviation from linearity occurs as the crack lengths become very small, for in this region transition from bundle to possible cumulative failure mode is taking place.

As discussed previously [12], curves obtained by assuming a critical fracture toughness value can be used to describe failure of these fiber reinforced composites. A superficial examination of curves, also included in the figures, might suggest that a critical stress intensity factor approach can be advanced in order to provide an alternative description of the reported data. For, as can be observed, curves generated using K_{Ic} values of about 66 and 30 $\text{ksi}\sqrt{\text{in}}$ pass reasonably close to the data points, particularly those at the larger crack lengths.

This conclusion is rather imprecise however, and lacks a clear fundamental failure mechanism that is based on any obvious materials parameter.

Further insight into the concept of crack propagation by a bundle mechanism can be achieved by noting the results obtained from twelve inch long specimens. The strength of a bundle of fibers of this length can be evaluated from (3) and the corresponding strength of notched specimens failing by a bundle mechanism is included in the figures. Since this curve is far below the experimental values obtained it can be concluded that the length of the bundle which fails at the crack tip does not vary with the total length of the specimen. Intuitive reasoning would tend to predict this result, for the plastic zone dimensions are more probably determined by the matrix yield strength, applied stress and the crack length. In any case, it can be concluded that the calculation of strength bounds based on the strength of bundles with a length equal to the total specimen length appears to be incorrect.

It should also be noted that the strength of a parallel sided test piece was not reduced when the gauge length of the specimen was increased from 3 to 9 inches (ie. total specimen length increasing from 6 to 12 inches). Failure by the crack propagation mode as discussed in (i) inherently assumes that a critical crack length exists which will produce unstable crack propagation. Cracks of this critical size will be reached at lower loads in longer specimens (see ref. 7). Thus, in contrast to the results included here the expected failure stress of longer specimens should be smaller.

iii. Proposed Fracture Model.

The proposed model is an extension of that originally used by Rosen to describe the basic failure mode of unnotched specimens of fiber reinforced materials. Essentially, it makes use of the shear lag analysis to suggest that in a three dimensional composite, load must be transferred around the break in a single fiber or around the break in a multifiber bundle by shear of the matrix. In a metallic material the length of matrix, l , necessary to achieve this transfer can be calculated, disregarding elastic effects, by using the expression [21] [22] for one broken fiber:

$$l = (D\sigma)/(4\tau) \quad \text{--8}$$

and, for n broken fibers

$$l = (nD\sigma)/(4\tau) \quad \text{-- 9}$$

where r is the fiber radius, σ is the stress in all the fibers at some distance from the break and τ is the shear yield strength of the matrix. The length analogous to the "ineffective" length discussed by Rosen is δ where $\delta = 2l$.

* The assumptions inherent in this model have been fully discussed in a recent paper by Zweben, Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Vol.6, 1974, pps.1-10c.

All fibers contained within this length of composite on either side of the crack or slot will be overloaded and, if the matrix or matrix fiber bond strength is not exceeded, failure will be expected to occur there. If the shear strength of the matrix is effectively zero (ie. air), then the ineffective length is infinite and the strength of the notched composite will be that given by the strength of a bundle of fibers with a length equal to the gauge length of the specimen. The strength of a composite will be greater than this if the matrix shear strength is greater than zero. In addition, any splitting of the matrix parallel to the fiber axis, as sometimes occurs at the crack tip can be considered to increase δ by an amount equal to the length of the split.

It is also reasonable to assume that, within the plastic zone, the first fibers adjacent to the broken ones will all tend to be uniformly stressed and will tend to support the greatest load except for the specific condition of total matrix splitting or $\tau = 0$. Thus, if the bundle of fibers that are spaced along the crack front fails, the total composite will tend to fail. Now the strength of a bundle of fibers of length L is given by (3) as:

$$\sigma_B = \sigma_o [L/D \omega e]^{-1/\omega}$$

If the tensile load bearing contribution of the matrix is ignored, then the strength of a notched composite σ_{CS} will be given by the expression

$$\sigma_{CS} = \sigma_B V_f (w - 2a)/w \quad \text{--10}$$

In addition, from (9)

$$L = \delta = 2\ell = (D n \sigma_c) / (2\tau V_f) \quad \text{--11}$$

when σ_c is the stress on the composite.

Values of L can be calculated to enable a value of σ_B , and hence a value of the tensile strength of a notched composite, σ_{CS} , to be calculated. As discussed in [11] values of L and σ_B are not independent. Thus, compatible values have to be obtained iteratively. Using a value of τ of 14.7 ksi [23] for both the 47 and 27 volume percent boron containing material, values of σ_{CS} were calculated and these are denoted as the shear lag curves in the figures. The agreement between these curves and the experimental results appears to substantiate the proposed model. As can be seen, the curves allow the full range of strength values to be calculated even for crack lengths as small as that associated with one fiber break. Lower strengths will be exhibited if splitting of the matrix parallel to the fiber axis occurs at the crack tip. However, for the larger crack

sizes, the shear lag curve and the bundle strength curve become coincident if the length of the test specimens is limited.

Inspection of the fracture specimens indicated that the matrix of many of the specimens had split for a short distance parallel to the fiber axis at or near to the original crack tip. This splitting was most severe in the SiC reinforced material, for multiple splits were observed and extensive fiber pull out had occurred. As can be noted in fig 3, the failure stress of this material always approached the strength of a simple bundle, even for the unnotched specimens. This observation indicated that stress transfer through the matrix was minimal for this material; thus the shear lag, Hedgepeth and K_c curves were not computed.

Conclusion

A model has been proposed that enables upper and lower strength bounds to be calculated for composite materials. The calculations are based on the statistical strength description of the fibers, their dimensions, the shear yield strength of the matrix and the length of the specimen. The calculations can be carried out for both notched and unnotched specimens. However, it is suggested that the extent of fiber-matrix unbonding effectively determines the specific strength of individual specimens within the calculated stress bounds.

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Legend

Figures 1 & 2

- ⌋ 6 in long, Solution treated specimens
- 6 in long, T6 age hardened specimens
- △ 12 in long, as-received specimens
- 6 in long, 0.040 in thick, as-received specimens
- × 6 in long 0.060 in thick, as-received specimens
- 6 in long 0.086 in thick, as-received specimens

Figure 3

- 34 v/o SiC reinforced specimens
- 40 v/o boron 0/90° cross-plyed specimens

All Figures
Curves

- 1 Hedgepeth curve
- 2 Shear Lag
- 3 3" long bundle strength
- 4 12" long bundle strength
- † unbroken

Fig. 1: The Effect of Crack Length On The Failure Stress of a Unidirectionally Reinforced 47 v/o Boron- 6061 Aluminum Composite.

Fig. 2: The Effect of Crack Length on the Failure Stress of a Unidirectionally Reinforced 27 v/o Boron-6061 Aluminum Composite.

Fig. 3: The Effect of Crack Length on the Failure Stress of a 6061 Aluminum Matrix Reinforced with 34 v/o Unidirectional SiC Fibers or 40 v/o 0/90° Cross-plyed Boron Fibers.